

N. gonorrhoea activates NOD2 in the human fallopian tube.

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We measured total transcription in the human fallopian tube following infection with *Neisseria gonorrhoea* to identify without bias major cellular factors required or important for gram-negative infection. NOD2 was the major pattern recognition receptor activated by *N. gonorrhoea*. Signaling mediators downstream of NOD2 were also major components of the *N. gonorrhoea* signature. NOD2 activation was accompanied by induction of the receptor intermediate kinase RIPK2. NOD2 signaling and activation of RIPK2 by *N. gonorrhoea* in the fallopian tube featured induction of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1b, TNF-alpha and IL-6. Inflammatory cytokine induction by NOD2 activation was concomitant with induction of prostaglandin and eicosanoid biosynthesis (e.g., PTGS2), and induction of receptor subunits for IL-17 and IL-23. We demonstrate here thus that NOD2 is likely an authentic innate immune receptor for *N. gonorrhoea* in humans.

Citations

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